

GEOGRAPHICAL SCIENCES

MONITORING THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON LOCAL ECOSYSTEMS

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Abstract

Climate change has a profound impact on entire ecosystems, leading to the extinction or migration of species, the occurrence of extreme weather events, reduced soil fertility, water shortages and droughts, an increase in natural disasters such as floods, the drying up and disappearance of certain rivers, the melting of glaciers, and an overall disruption of ecological balance.

Keywords: climate, local, ecosystem, monitoring, change.

Introduction

The use of satellite imagery to monitor climate change and its impact on ecosystems in Azerbaijan represents a highly effective approach. Below is an overview of how satellite imagery and remote sensing technologies are applied in ecosystem monitoring:

1. Satellite imagery enables continuous observation of environmental changes over time, covering extensive geographical areas.
2. In Azerbaijan, satellite data is used to study and analyze changes in local ecosystems and natural resources.
3. Satellite technologies allow for the tracking of surface heat and temperature fluctuations across various regions.

4. Remote sensing tools facilitate the analysis of changes in precipitation intensity and regional drought conditions.

5. Satellite imagery is used to observe changes in land use, such as the expansion or reduction of arable land, as well as shifts in vegetation types.

6. It helps to analyze ice and snow cover. The melting of glaciers in Azerbaijan's mountainous regions and its ecological consequences are monitored using satellite data.

7. Allows to monitor water resource. Changes in rivers, lakes, and other water bodies—including variations in water levels and quality—are tracked through satellite observations.

Table 1.

Satellite Images and the Impact of Climate Change on Ecosystems

Effects	The importance of satellite imagery
Increasing drought	Satellite images show increasing drought, especially in southern and central Azerbaijan
Biodiversity loss	Based on satellite data, it can be determined which species are under pressure due to climate change.
Soil erosion and reduction of agricultural land	Satellite images track soil erosion and productivity decline in Azerbaijan

Based on satellite imagery, it is essential to develop targeted strategies to combat climate change and prepare appropriate adaptation measures for each region, guided by predictive data. Satellite observations help identify the negative impacts of climate change on local areas, designate new agricultural zones, and support improvements in irrigation systems. In Azerbaijan, satellite imagery has been utilized to study local forest resources, land cover, and biodiversity in regions such as Ganja-Gazakh, Karabakh, and Guba-Khachmaz. These studies also addressed drought and water scarcity, as well as broader ecological transformations

driven by climatic factors. Based on the findings, suitable solutions have been proposed to mitigate these effects.

Let us consider how satellite imagery has been used to monitor changes in mountain lake areas in Azerbaijan as a function of climate variability:

When monitoring the effects of global climate change on the Republic of Azerbaijan, satellite data reveals dynamic changes in snow cover, glacier extent, reservoir surface area, desertification, drought severity, and mountain lake coverage.

Research conducted by "Azercosmos" OJSC focused on the Boyuk Alagol, Ishikli Karagol, and Kichik

Alagol lakes, located in the recently liberated territories. The findings indicate that global climate change

has led to substantial and dynamic alterations in the surface area of these lakes, presenting serious environmental challenges.

Table 1.

Dynamics of Monthly Changes in the Area of Lake Boyuk Alagol Over Five Years (hectares)

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
January	465.4	435.2	430.2	472.8	402.2
February	450.5	435.1	430.2	468.7	409.1
March	433.3	432.1	471.9	468.7	401.4
April	435.6	432.1	471.7	411.5	350.8

It is noteworthy that this research was conducted on 30 mountain lakes located in the liberated Kalbajar, Lachin, and Aghdara (Ağdere) districts, an area of 2 hectares. The total area of mountain lakes studied in these districts is approximately 900 hectares. The largest of these, comprising 72% of the total area, are Boyuk Alagol (Kalbajar), Ishikli Garagol (Lachin), and Kichik Alagol (Kalbajar).

Based on statistics, we can say that the area of the lake decreased by 63.2 ha between January 2020 (465.4 ha) and January 2024 (402.2 ha). A decrease of 41.4 ha was observed in February, 31.9 ha in March, and 84.8 ha in April. Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) were used in this study. Monthly satellite images of field changes in these lakes at different dates were collected and constitute the main dataset of the study.

Azerbaijan continues to contribute to the entire world in the fight against climate change by hosting events such as COP29 and being active in fulfilling its commitments.

As we know, general water resources are very important for the entire ecosystem components in the world. Despite their great vital importance for all nature and living things, water resources are subject to very large anthropogenic impacts, and various reasons such as drought caused by global warming are creating major problems. Since the beginning of the 21st century, negative factors such as the annual rate of precipitation in all parts of the world's water resources (oceans, seas, lakes, rivers, glaciers, etc.) and the sharp change in the areas of water basins have been alarmingly affected by all the consequences of climate change. An increase in the average temperature of water resources is observed. Of course, this situation leads to changes in the area of water resources. Lakes, which are an important component of land units, constitute up to 1% of the water resources of the hydrosphere. Despite having a very small percentage, these freshwater resources play an important role in the sustainable existence of the living environment in the ecosystem. Baku hosted an important event such as COP29 to solve such negative effects caused by climate change and examined ways to solve it. The emergence of sharp differences in water masses brings steps to be taken in this direction to the fore. The continuous increase in negative impacts leads to the activity and dynamism of this process. Remote Sensing has played a key role in investigating, studying and finding solutions to such global problems. This method obtains comprehensive information about the area without forcing observation on the ground, without physically observing the area. Remote sensing is used

in a number of fields (military, humanitarian, geographical research). During its use, areas are studied using signals transmitted from the ground and aerosensor technologies are used. It is possible to collect visual information from the most dangerous and difficult-to-pass places through remote sensing.

Using satellite data, the detection and study of spatial changes in existing inaccessible water resources has become a key factor. Various artificial intelligence technologies are also of particular importance.

The main topic of this article is to investigate the factors that cause spatial changes in the inaccessible mountainous lakes of Azerbaijan, to visually observe how they change over the months. These lakes, along with their enchanting beauty and picturesque appearance, are striking in their inaccessibility, which has led to the under-research of these water resources. The territory of the Kalbajar-Lachin economic geographical region (in Kalbajar and Lachin), the territory of the Karabakh economic geographical region (Aghdara region) was taken as the object of research. Considering that these territories were under enemy occupation for a long time, the lack of attention to these territories is also evident in the lack of modern research work. The fact that foreigners were content with living, exploiting, and plundering in these territories once again proves their carelessness towards these territories, their lack of being original and eternal inhabitants.

The statistical result of the dynamic area change of water mass in lakes across the country was determined based on the studies conducted in 2020-2024. Let's look at the 5-year study example through the following illustration.

In addition, research was conducted on 30 mountain lakes covering an area of 2 ha in the territories of Kalbajar, Lachin and Ağdere. The total area of mountain lakes in that area is 900 ha. The largest lakes, covering 72% of the area, are Boyuk Alagol (Kalbajar), Ishikli Karagol (Lachin), Kichik Alagol (Kalbajar). Boyuk Alagol is located in the territory of the Karabakh volcanic plateau, in the Kalbajar region - 40°00' N. E. 45°44' N. W. geographical coordinates. The height of the lake is 2729 m above sea level. The maximum length is 3.7 km, and the widest is more than 9 m. Its volume is 24.3 million m³. The area of the lake is 5.1 km², and its length is 3670 m. The widest part is 2875 m, the average width is 1365 m, and the maximum depth is 9.4 m. There are also about 30 small lakes in this area, the largest of which is Kichik Alagöl after Boyuk Alagöl. Most of them dry up in the summer. The largest river is the Gurbagalı River, and 7 rivers flow

into the lake. Kichik Alagol is located at the geographical coordinates of 39°59'11" N. E. 45°44'01" N. W. The area of the lake is 0.9 km², and its length is 2000 m. The widest part is 825 m, and the length of the coastline is 5260 m. The deepest place is 4 m. Let's compare the difference in change for the first 4 months of 2020

and 2024. The area of the lake decreased by 63.2 ha between January 2020 (465.4 ha) and January 2024 (402.2 ha). A decrease of 41.4 ha was observed in February, 31.9 ha in March, and 84.8 ha in April. Let's look at the illustration below.

Pic.1 Description of the area change of Boyuk Alagol for January 2020/2024 (ha)

Based on the above description, we can say that the satellite image taken in 2020 and 2024 is the most important dynamic change image obtained within the scope of the study and forms the main part of the study. The satellite image from May 2021 shows the upper

limit of the lake (497.5 ha), that is, the image with the largest area. The smallest area change was recorded in April 2024 (350.8 ha).

Let's look at the differences in the dynamics of change by looking at satellite images of Lake Kichik Alagol over the years.

Table 2.

Dynamics of monthly changes in the area of Kichik Alagol over 5 years (ha)

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
January	59.1	58.8	58.8	55.9	75.6
February	59.1	59	58.8	55.9	84
March	57.2	58.8	58.8	55	74.2
April	14.8	59	58.8	62.5	69.5

As can be seen, the monthly change statistics of Kichik Alagol over the past 5 years are shown in the table. According to the table, we can say that the lowest dynamic area change was recorded in April 2020, November 2021, August 2022, November 2023, and April 2024.

In the studies conducted by year, the highest area increase (in ha) was recorded in January, February, March, and April 2024. An area change of 16.5 ha was observed in January, 24.9 ha in February, 17 ha in March, and 54.7 ha in April.

Table 3.

Dynamics of monthly changes in the area of Lake Işıklı Garagol over 5 years (ha)

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Yanvar	166.5	165	163.4	188.1	162.4
Fevral	165.4	166	166.6	163.4	164.8
Mart	166.5	166	166.5	188.1	169.8
Aprel	169.1	168.3	169.2	161.7	177.1

Table 3 - we can basically say that the lowest area indicator was recorded in October 2023 (161.2 ha), and

the highest description indicator was recorded in May 2022 (190.7ha).

Pic. 2 Description of area change for Işıklı Garagol for January 2020/2024 (ha)

The first image was recorded in January 2020, and the second image was recorded in January 2024. Based on the image above, we can say that an area change of 4 ha was recorded between the 2020 image and the 2024 image.

The precise information we have obtained based on the research conducted once again shows the importance of Geographic Information Systems. Because in our modern era, they are of great importance not only in investigating the problems created by global warming and finding solutions, but also in solving all ecological problems.

Drought is a significant global issue affecting water availability, agriculture, natural resources, and human living standards, often resulting in the degradation or collapse of entire ecosystems. To assess drought levels in the Republic of Azerbaijan, satellite imagery is regularly acquired and analyzed. Data from the past 25 years have revealed the detrimental effects of drought on vegetation across the country. According to recent assessments, the three economic-geographical regions most affected by drought in Azerbaijan are East Zangezur, Karabakh, and Sheki-Zagatala. Key contributing factors include climate change, inefficient water use in agriculture, and increasing water demand driven by population growth. The primary indicators of drought

severity include a reduction in average annual precipitation, an increase in the number of dry months, and fluctuations in the water levels of reservoirs, rivers, and lakes. One of the most effective strategies for mitigating the impact of drought is soil and water conservation. Healthy, well-managed soil is more capable of absorbing rainfall and contributes to more efficient water use. Drought impacts extend beyond the depletion of water resources and reduced soil fertility; they also lead to disruptions in the ecological balance, directly affecting human health and quality of life. The causes and consequences of drought vary depending on regional climatic, geographic, and economic conditions.

Comprehensive Monitoring of the Caspian Sea: The current ecological condition of the Caspian Sea, under the influence of climate change, has been assessed through satellite imagery. Studies have been conducted on changes in sea level, and preventive action plans have been developed. Space-based monitoring of the Azerbaijani sector of the Caspian Sea is crucial for understanding the ecological environment, tracking global pollution trends, and supporting sustainable economic development. Data from NASA's AQUA and TERRA satellites were used for ecological monitoring of the Caspian Sea over the period 2002–2024.

Graphic: Water Surface Temperature of the Caspian Sea, August 2002–2024

Pic.3. Description: The satellite imagery below illustrates temperature changes in the Caspian Sea from 2002 to 2024, with temperature increases depicted in shades of orange.

Conclusion

Satellite imagery plays a critical role in addressing key challenges such as mitigating the adverse effects of climate change, monitoring natural disasters, tracking deforestation, analyzing sea level changes, identifying sources of pollution, assessing plant health, and forecasting agricultural yields. In the modern world, satellite data serve as an indispensable tool across numerous fields. In sectors such as agriculture, urban planning, and emergency response, satellite imagery provides rapid, accurate, and comprehensive insights.

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